

THE MAGNETIC STUDY OF PERIODATES. PART I THE STRUCTURE OF PERIODIC ACID

BY SUNDEE LAL AGGARWAL AND SURJIT SINGH

Magnetic susceptibility of periodic acid has been determined both in the solid state as well as in solution. The values tally with each other quite well. From this the acid appears to exist both in the solid state as well as in solution as $\text{HIO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The metallic periodates correspond to a number of periodic acids but H_5IO_6 is the only one known in the solid state. This may either be regarded as metaperiodic acid dihydrate, $\text{HIO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, or as paraperiodic acid, H_5IO_6 (Mellor, "Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry," Vol. II, p. 386). The acid on dehydration at low pressure yields HIO_4 which accords with its formulation as $\text{HIO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Lamb, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1902, 27, 134; Partington and Bahl, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1088). The polybasic character of the acid however favours the formula H_5IO_6 (Rosenheim and Lowenthal, *Kolloid Z.*, 1919, 25, 53; Giolitti, *Gazzetta*, 1902, 32, 340; Ostwald, *J. prat. Chem.*, 1885, 32, 311).

We have determined the magnetic susceptibilities of the periodic acid in the solid state and in solutions of different concentrations with a view to ascertaining its constitution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Secondary Sodium Paraperiodate.— $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$ was prepared by the method of Partington and Bahl (*J. Chem. Soc.* 1934, 1086). (Found : I, 46.21 ; Na, 16.57 ; O, 19.8. $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$ requires I, 46.69 ; Na, 16.91 per cent and the decomposition $4\text{Na}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6 = 4\text{Na}_2\text{O} + 2\text{I}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O} + 7\text{O}_2$ requires O, 20.58 per cent).

Silver Mesoperiodate.— Ag_3IO_6 was prepared by adding a thin suspension of $\text{Na}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$ to a boiling solution of silver nitrate (Wells, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1901, 28, 278). (Found : Ag, 62.35 ; O, 15.15. Ag_3IO_6 requires Ag, 61.0 and the decomposition $2\text{Ag}_3\text{IO}_6 = \text{AgI} + 4\text{Ag} + 5\text{O}_2$ requires O, 14.87 per cent).

Periodic acid was prepared by suspending silver mesoperiodate in water and passing a current of chlorine in it until the whole of black silver periodate was converted into silver chloride. The filtrate from AgCl was concentrated upon a water-bath at 60—70° which on keeping in vacuum desiccator over CaCl_2 deposited monoclinic crystals of periodic acid. The solid after crystallisation and drying over P_2O_5 gave I, 55.10% ; O, 24.7 ; H_5IO_6 requires I, 55.7 per cent and the decomposition $4\text{H}_5\text{IO}_6 = 10\text{H}_2\text{O} + 2\text{I}_2 + 7\text{O}_2$ requires O, 24.51 per cent).

Potassium metaperiodate was prepared as by Bahl and Surjit Singh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 167).

Susceptibility determinations.—The susceptibilities were measured by the modified Guoy's method (Negri, *Current Sci.*, 1935). Conductivity water ($\chi_m = -0.722 \times 10^{-6}$) was used as the reference substance. Determinations on compounds of known susceptibilities are reported in Table I. The maximum difference is within 0.3%.

TABLE I

Substance.	Mean of three observations.	Reported value (Inter. Crit. Tables).	Deviation.
$-\chi^m/g.$			
Potassium chloride	0.515×10^{-6}	0.516×10^{-6}	0.2%
Naphthalene	0.718	0.717	0.2
Ethyl alcohol (34°)	0.744	0.744	0.0
Camphoric anhydride	0.622	0.620	0.3
1 : 3 : 5-Trinitrobenzene	0.351	0.352	0.3

The susceptibilities of potassium metaperiodate, sodium paraperiodate and periodic acid in the solid state are given in Table II. The susceptibilities of the solutions of the acid are tabulated in Table III along with calculated values of susceptibility of the solute from the relation,

$$\chi_{\text{Solution}} = \chi_{\text{Solute}} - C_s + (1 - C_s) \chi_{\text{solvent}}$$

C_s is the weight of the solute per g. of the solution.

TABLE II

Substances.	$-\chi^m/g$	$-\chi^m/g \text{ mol.}$
Potassium metaperiodate (KIO_4)	0.303×10^{-6}	66.7×10^{-6}
Sodium paraperiodate ($\text{Na}_2\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6$)	0.261	70.29
Periodic acid (H_5IO_6 or $\text{HIO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$)	0.313	71.36

TABLE III

Conc.	Density.	C_s	$-\chi_m \times 10^6$ of soln.	$-\chi \times 10^6$ of solute.	$-\chi \times 10^6$ per g. mol. of solute.
1.701N	1.285	0.3018	0.5947	0.305	69.50
1.392	1.234	0.2576	0.6109	0.297	67.44
1.121	1.189	0.2149	0.6346	0.322	73.45
0.804	1.134	0.1616	0.6543	0.314	71.53
0.705	1.116	0.1441	0.6609	0.310	70.58
					Mean — 70.5

DISCUSSION

The molecular susceptibility of a polar salt may be considered as the sum of the susceptibilities of the ions,

$$\chi_m = \chi_{\text{cation}} + \chi_{\text{anion}}$$

The ionic susceptibilities have been derived from a number of different methods and also from theoretical consideration. Miss Trew reviewed the various methods (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1941, 37, 476) and gave an average set of values for ionic susceptibilities derived from experimental results. The average ionic susceptibilities for Na and K ions are -6.8×10^{-6} and -14.9×10^{-6} in most of their salts. Hydrogen ion is generally considered to have zero ionic susceptibility in the solid acids.

The molecular susceptibilities of H_2IO_4 and HIO_4 can therefore be calculated from the χ_m values of $Na_2H_2IO_4$ and KIO_4 by subtracting for two Na^+ ions and one K^+ ion respectively. The values so calculated come to be -56.69×10^{-6} for H_2IO_4 and -51.8×10^{-6} for HIO_4 . This calculated value for H_2IO_4 is very much divergent from the experimental χ_m of periodic acid (Table II). The periodic acid therefore does not possess the structure H_2IO_4 . On similar lines the χ_m for $HIO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ can be calculated, by summing the above calculated values of χ_m HIO_4 (-51.8×10^{-6}) and χ_m of two molecules of water ($1 \times -12.96 \times 10^{-6}$). This works out to be -77.72×10^{-6} . Taking into account the depression in diamagnetism due to existence of water molecules as water of hydration, this calculated value of $HIO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ is in good agreement with the experimental value of -71.36×10^{-6} (Table III). The χ_m of the acid both in the solid and in its solutions is equal within experimental error. Thus periodic acid both in the solid state and in its solutions exists as $HIO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
GOVERNMENT COLLEGE, LAHORE.
AND
DOABA COLLEGE, JULLUNDUR.
